

Brussels-Zaventem

BRU

This fiche includes maps displaying the location of the sampling points (SPOs) around the airport of Brussels (BRU) with measurements of NO₂ and PM_{2.5} in 2023 (E1a validated data AQ e-Reporting). The tables include additional information on the annual mean concentrations of each SPO with available data (data coverage larger than 75%), distances of the SPOs from the airport area, location of the SPO in one of the 8 wind sectors around the airport (WS: N, NE, E, SE, S, SW, W, NW), wind frequency blowing from the airport in that WS, population living in the WS within 10 km from the airport, and trends of annual mean concentrations (2005-2023) when available. This information has been complemented with the EEA air quality annual maps (1 km x 1 km), covering the whole area around the airport and showing in the boxplot the different levels concentrations over the airport area compared to the surrounding region, including the weighted area means for the different land cover classes.

The presented information is based only on SPOs reported to the EEA, additional SPOs or data may exist at national level.

Brussels-BRU

Airport area and NO₂ air quality SPOs around the airport within 5 and 10 km

Airport area and PM_{2.5} air quality SPOs around the airport within 5, 10 and 20 km

Pozzoli, L., Gerwig, H., Gressent, A., Soares, J., Colette, A., & Monge, S. (2025). Air quality around airports (Eionet Report – ETC HE 2025/7, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17432053>).
[ETC HE Report 2025/7: Air quality around airports — Eionet Portal](#)

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NO₂ SPOs in 2023 around the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Belgium	BELSZ01	Industrial	50.91	4.50	16.23		0.00	NE	31.87	18,846
Belgium	BELSZ05	Background	50.92	4.52	13.03		0.60	NE	31.87	18,846
Belgium	BETMEU1	Background	50.90	4.40	16.95	-45.74	3.17	W	7.41	125,345
Belgium	BETE008	Industrial	50.93	4.40	12.44		4.29	NW	5.08	49,540
Belgium	BETN043	Industrial	50.88	4.38	22.27	-41.82	4.39	W	7.41	125,345
Belgium	BETR020	Background	50.94	4.44	15.94	-54.87	4.48	NW	5.08	49,540
Belgium	BETE009	Industrial	50.95	4.44	11.14		5.91	NW	5.08	49,540

PM_{2.5} SPOs in 2023 around the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Belgium	BELSZ05	Background	50.92	4.52	9.67		0.60	NE	31.87	18,846
Belgium	BETMEU1	Background	50.90	4.40	10.35		3.17	W	7.41	125,345
Belgium	BETN043	Industrial	50.88	4.38	10.61	-57.68	4.39	W	7.41	125,345
Belgium	BETR020	Background	50.94	4.44	9.63		4.48	NW	5.08	49,540
Belgium	BETREG1	Traffic	50.84	4.37	9.77		8.07	SW	11.28	307,376
Belgium	BETR001	Background	50.85	4.33	9.64	-67.70	9.29	SW	11.28	307,376
Belgium	BETR842	Traffic	51.02	4.48	10.19		11.48	N	15.86	23,517
Belgium	BETB011	Background	50.86	4.29	9.49	-49.07	11.61	W	7.41	125,345
Belgium	BETR012	Background	50.80	4.36	8.54	-66.28	12.76	SW	11.28	307,376

Annual mean NO₂ concentrations in 2023

EEA air quality map (1 km x 1 km)

Concentrations over the airport area compared to the surrounding region. Coloured dots correspond to weighted area means for different land cover classes in the surrounding region.

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Annual mean PM_{2.5} concentrations in 2023

EEA air quality map (1 km x 1 km)

Concentrations over the airport area compared to the surrounding region. Coloured dots correspond to weighted area means for different land cover classes in the surrounding region.

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